

US WOMEN WRITERS IN 19-20TH CENTURIES

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Abstract. Literature is a kind of art, a cultural phenomenon, writing, which occupies a certain place in the life of any people, of all mankind. Literature is a reflection of the soul, emotions, experiences of the author, it is the visiting card of the people, the nation. At all times, people wanted to touch the sublime, they strove for knowledge, turned to the works of great writers, poets, playwrights. We comprehend the spirit of the times in literature, we draw from it the patterns of movement, the problems of development, we learn how the people lived and live, we learn their mentality. Literature can be epistolary, scientific, artistic. And the genres are different: fiction, detective stories, children's literature, dramaturgy, classics, mysticism, poetry, journalism, religion and spirituality, fantasy, humor and satire and others. In this article you will read about US women writers in 20 th century and their talent for language skills, developed fantasy.

Key words: Literature, women, journalism, religion, fantasy, humor, poem, prose, poetry, book, memories, contribution, writer.

ЖЕНЩИНЫ-ПИСАТЕЛЬНИЦЫ США В 19-20 ВЕКАХ

Аннотация. Литература - это вид искусства, культурное явление, письменность, которая занимает определенное место в жизни любого народа, всего человечества. Литература - это отражение души, эмоций, переживаний автора, это визитная карточка народа, нации. Во все времена люди хотели прикоснуться к возвышенному, они стремились к знаниям, обращались к произведениям великих писателей, поэтов, драматургов. Мы постигаем дух времени в литературе, мы черпаем из нее закономерности движения, проблемы развития, мы узнаем, как жили и здравствуют люди, мы изучаем их менталитет. Литература может быть эпистолярной, научной, художественной. И жанры разные: художественная литература, детективы, детская литература, драматургия, классика, мистика, поэзия, журналистика, религия и духовность, фэнтези, юмор и сатира и другие. В этой статье вы прочтете о женщинах-писательницах США в 20 веке и их таланте к языковым навыкам, развитой фантазии.

Ключевые слова: литература, женщины, журналистика, религия, фэнтези, юмор, стихотворение, проза, поэзия, книга, воспоминания, вклад, писательница.

A woman must master the art of seduction, because she is the keeper of the hearth, the continuer of the family and species. In addition to the art of seduction, the writer must also have a talent for language skills, a developed fantasy ... They read because women have no equal in the art of seduction. Because the area of feelings is the subject of the liveliest interest of any normal person. Because stories “about love” resonate in the soul of any person, regardless of gender, age and nationality. At first let us remember about following earlier women writers in the US:

Louisa May Alcott (born Louisa May Alcott; 1832 - 1888) was an American writer who became famous for her 1868 novel Little Women, which was based on memories of her growing up in the company of three sisters. The book was written at the request of Boston publisher Thomas

Niles, who asked Alcott to write a "book for girls". Meg was based on her older sister Anna, herself as Jo, and Beth and Amy were based on her younger sisters Elizabeth and May, respectively. The success of the book prompted the writer to compose several novels related to this work: in 1869 a sequel was published called "Good Wives", which is often published together with the first part of the novel and tells about the youth of the March sisters and their marriage; in 1871, the book "Little Men" was published, also autobiographical, telling about the writer's nephews; finally, in 1886, The Joe Boys was published. In addition, many of Olcott's later stories and novellas echoed Little Women. Unlike Jo March, her literary incarnation, Louisa May Alcott never married. Louisa May Alcott's "Little Women" and "The Good Wives" are, without exaggeration, some of the best-known classic American literature for young adults. These sincere, touching books about the childhood and youth of four sisters, published one after another in 1868-1869, have gone through an incredible number of editions, and are very popular today; based on them, stage and cinematic versions were created, in one of which the role of Joe is played by the famous actress Katharine Hepburn.

Anna Bradstreet (eng. Anne Bradstreet, 1612-1672) - the first American poetess. Bradstreet's only lifetime book of poems, *The Tenth Muse Newly Appeared in America*, was published without an author's name in London (1650). The edition of "Selected Poems" prepared by her, including the most famous - the poem "To My Dear and Loving Husband", was published in America after her death (1678). The religious poems of Bradstreet enjoyed a certain popularity among the Puritan pioneers who copied them, but later they were forgotten and printed only in the middle of the 19th century. J. Berryman's poem *Tribute to Anna Bradstreet* (1953), highly appreciated by American critics, is dedicated to the poetess. She herself spoke of poetry: "the place of my solitude." Her book of poetry, published without her knowledge in 1650 in London by her half-brother (under the pretentious title of *The Tenth Muse Newly Appeared in America: The Delightful Fruits of Versatile Mind and Learning*), caused a sensation in both England, New and Old. The "scientific" poetry of A. Bradstreet, included in this volume, reveals the author's good orientation in philosophical systems, her inquisitive intellect and confident command of the techniques of versification; it is solid, monumental and secondary, which is why it is perceived today as a skillful imitation of contemporary English poets. She wrote a lot, and not only prose and poetry, she also found time to reflect her thoughts in the form of aphorisms, quotes, catchphrases, here is one of them: "If there were no winter, spring would not seem so beautiful to us; if there were no poverty, wealth would not be so desirable."

Harriet Elizabeth Beecher Stowe (born Harriet Elizabeth Beecher Stowe; 1811-1896) was an American writer, author of the famous novel *Uncle Tom's Cabin*. In her literary works, she acted as a benefactor of women's education and the destruction of slavery. In response to the curses and accusations that fell on Beecher Stowe for this preaching of the liberation of the Negroes by the slave owners and their friends, she published the "Key" ("Key to Uncle Tom's Cabin"), in which she clearly proved that the plot for the novel directly taken by her from life, often even to the smallest detail. Beecher Stowe's poems are predominantly written on religious themes. She also wrote quotes and aphorisms. Here is one of them: "The most bitter tears over the grave pour over unspoken words and unfinished deeds." Harriet Beecher Stowe is an American writer and educator. U.S. President Abraham Lincoln called her "the little woman who started the big war." The problem of the liberation of the Negroes, of the choice of a peaceful or hostile path, is also

discussed in another book by the author, whose name is "Dred, the story of the damned swamp." In other novels, the writer also dealt with social issues, women's education, women's equality.

Emily Elizabeth Dickinson (born Emily Elizabeth Dickinson; 1830-1886) was an American poet. During her lifetime, she published less than ten poems (most sources give numbers from seven to ten) out of one thousand eight hundred written by her. Dickinson's poems have no analogues in contemporary poetry. Their lines are short, titles are generally missing, and unusual punctuation and capitalization are common. Many of her poems contain the motif of death and immortality, the same plots permeate her letters to friends. Currently, Emily Dickinson is regarded by critics as one of the greatest American poets. by illness. Emily was very educated and well-read. She studied English, Latin, literature, history, botany, geology, psychology and arithmetic. Emily's poems have attracted many composers, including Samuel Barber, Elliott Carter, Aaron Copland, Andre Previn, Michael Tilson Thomas, Ned Rorem, Osvaldo Golikhov. Dickinson spoke beautiful English, a rich and vivid imagination, which may be why the poems of the poetess are unforgettable, impressionable, full of feelings.

*A flower follows the sun with its gaze, and in the evening, noticing nearby
With the eyes of a flower,
It grumbles, bending low: "Why are you sitting close to me?" "Because life is sweet!"
We are all flowers, and You are the light!
Forgive us if we did not have enough days to love you, -
We are in love with your sunsets, In your flights and agates,
And at midnight ahead!
I especially like the following creation of the American poetess.
Success is tempting for those who are not fed up with it.
The nectar will soon be appreciated by the One Who is tormented by Thirst.
In the purple Army, who managed to take away the Flag from the enemy,
No Victory price.
Can't know better
Than that defeated soldier who was slain in battle
And I heard the sound of victorious trumpets, Falling into a mortal sleep.*

Edna St. Vincent Millay (eng. Edna St. Vincent Millay, 1892-1950) - American poetess and playwright, one of the most famous poets of the United States of the XX century. Born into a family of a nurse and a teacher, she grew up without a father, her mother traveled a lot with her daughters from city to city in search of work, taught them independence and love of literature. Edna's literary talents (or, as she preferred to call herself as a child, "Vincent") were revealed at a college in Camden, Maine, she began to print from the age of 15. In 1912, Millay's poem "Renascence" won fourth place in the US Poem of the Year competition, causing a scandal because everyone considered it deserving of first place; the winner admitted that he received the prize with displeasure, and the runner-up gave his award to Edna. After this story, Millay became a celebrity, and a wealthy woman, Caroline Doe, paid for the education of the poetess at Wasser College. After graduating in 1917, Edna moved to New York. In New York, Millay lived in Greenwich Village and led a free, bohemian life. Her fame grew. In 1923, her collection Harp Weaver and other poems won the Pulitzer Prize, the first time a woman had been awarded the prize for poetry. Millay is a master of the sonnet, ballads, in her form she was guided by classical traditions; echoes of the topic

of the day (the place of a woman in society, etc.) were also reflected in her work. Her reputation was negatively affected by patriotic poems written during the Second World War; Los Angeles Times critic Merle Rubin noted that "she seemed to provoke more American critics with her pro-democracy poetry than Ezra Pound with her pro-fascism poetry." Nevertheless, in 1943, during the war, Millay received the Robert Frost Medal for outstanding contributions to poetry.

Marianne Moore (Marianne Craig Moore, 1887-1972) is an American poet, one of the leading representatives of modernism, the winner of many awards (including the National Book Award and the Pulitzer Prize in 1951), who wrote in a peculiar, vivid manner that combined accuracy and richness with abundant citation and a rare ability to "put a variety of ideas into one, compact image. T.S. Eliot called Moore's work "a particle of that very rare substance that is called non-ephemeral modern poetry." Moore gained fame and popularity in the literary circles of New York, where she repeatedly took on the role of hostess at the mayor's receptions. She often attended boxing matches and baseball games, and was a big fan of Muhammad Ali, for whose album (I Am the Greatest!) She wrote the intro on the cover. Moore continued to publish in publications such as The Nation, The New Republic and Partisan Review. Each of these writers is unique in their own way, each of them, undoubtedly, left her own handwriting in the history of the development of American literature in the 20th century. Each of them and many others deserve to be called the "Pride of American Culture and Literature". A woman writer is always interesting, always a mystery. After all, every woman is first and foremost a person. This topic is very deep and extensive, so I want to continue my research in this area.

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